

Development of Industrial Artificial-Intelligence Systems in Production Environments: A Delphi Study on Benefits, Issues, Risks, and Mitigation Strategies

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Artificial-Intelligence Systems
Development
Configuration
Challenges
Manufacturing
Production
Delphi study

ABSTRACT

The adoption of industrial Artificial-Intelligence (AI) systems in production environments has increased considerably in recent years, enabling new forms of process automation, engineering support, and data-driven decision making. However, practitioner-oriented insights regarding their practical development, configuration, and operation remain limited. To address this gap, we conducted a four-round Delphi study with 26 practitioners involved in industrial AI systems in production-related environments. Using iterative expert assessments, thematic analysis, and consensus-oriented evaluation, the study synthesizes benefits, issues, risks, and mitigation strategies associated with industrial AI systems.

The findings indicate that industrial AI systems are increasingly evolving from isolated analytical models toward integrated and highly configurable production ecosystems. While experts associated AI systems with operational and economic benefits, they simultaneously emphasized challenges related to integration complexity, configurability, dependency management, traceability, lifecycle management, and governance. In particular, dependency hell, combinatorial explosion, and configuration mismatches emerged as recurring practical concerns.

Overall, the study suggests that many practical challenges of industrial AI systems no longer primarily emerge from model development itself, but from their integration and operation within heterogeneous production environments. We argue that our findings provide practice-oriented insights into the development, configuration, and operation of industrial AI systems.

1. Introduction

Industrial Artificial-Intelligence (AI) systems are increasingly integrated into production environments to support operational and engineering activities based on learning processes, such as production control, quality assurance, predictive maintenance, or process optimization (Scotti, 2019; Chryssolouris et al., 2023). In this context, their adoption is frequently associated with expectations regarding improvements in central strategic objectives of production, particularly product quality, production time, and operational costs. For example, industrial AI systems are expected to support faster and more adaptive decision making, reduce downtime, or improve process robustness (Monostori et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2018; Rakholia et al., 2024).

However, the development, configuration, and operation of industrial AI systems introduce substantial technical and organizational complexity (Elahi et al., 2023). Unlike

isolated software applications, industrial AI systems are commonly embedded into heterogeneous production environments involving interconnected and highly configurable software components with complex dependencies on hardware systems and individual devices (Schuh and Scholz, 2019; Peres et al., 2020; Serôdio et al., 2024). This tight cyber-physical integration increases the complexity of configuring, deploying, and operating industrial AI systems, since changes in software, hardware, or operational contexts may propagate across interconnected system components and production processes. Consequently, developing, configuring, and operating industrial AI systems becomes substantially more challenging in practice (Peres et al., 2020; Weber et al., 2023). For example, failures or inappropriate handling strategies may directly affect production continuity, system reliability and safety, operational efficiency, or product quality in production contexts (Steimers and Schneider, 2022; Sinha and Lee, 2024).

Prior research extensively investigates industrial AI technologies and application scenarios, including model and application development (Pimenov et al., 2023), digital twins (Bhambri et al., 2024), or Internet of Things environments (Khang et al., 2024). However, this body of work is often shaped by theory-oriented settings, prototypical implementations, or application-specific evaluations. In

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contrast, practitioner-based studies remain comparatively limited and frequently focus on specific domains, working areas, or use cases. We argue that broader practical experiences regarding industrial AI systems therefore remain insufficiently consolidated across industrial contexts. This gap is particularly relevant because the successful transfer of industrial AI research into production practice depends not only on technological advances, but also on a deeper understanding of practical experiences (e.g., adoption challenges) (Schuh and Scholz, 2019; Schuh et al., 2020; Scholz, 2022). At the same time, such practical perspectives become particularly valuable when they are not only collected once (e.g., through surveys), but systematically reflected upon, reconsidered, and consolidated through iterative assessments by experienced practitioners (e.g., Delphi study) (Hsu and Sandford, 2007). Hence, we argue that a structured synthesis of expert perspectives on industrial AI systems can contribute a broader empirical understanding of their development, configuration, and adoption in practice.

To address this research gap, we conducted a four-round Delphi study (Hsu and Sandford, 2007) with 26 experts involved in the development, configuration, and operation of industrial AI systems in production environments. Using iterative expert assessments and thematic analysis, the study investigates practical experiences, development and configuration-related challenges, perceived opportunities, and mitigation approaches associated with industrial AI systems. Based on the collected assessments, we derive implications for research and industrial practice.

Our contributions are summarized as follows:

- We conduct a Delphi study with experts involved in the development, configuration, and adoption of industrial AI systems in production environments to systematically capture and reassess practitioner experiences.
- We synthesize expert assessments based on a thematic analysis to provide relevant benefits, issues, risks and mitigation strategies from a software-engineering perspective.
- We identify and discuss theoretical and practical implications of the derived benefits, issues, risks and mitigation strategies.
- We provide an openly accessible repository containing the study data and supplementary research artifacts.¹

Our study's results suggests that industrial AI systems introduce opportunities and challenges that emerge throughout their integration into production environments and operational processes. Rather than being limited to isolated AI functionality, practitioner experiences are strongly connected to engineering activities, configuration practices, industrial infrastructures, and organizational conditions surrounding these systems. We expect that the insights obtained

from this study contribute to a more practice-oriented understanding of industrial AI systems and support future research as well as industrial decision making in production contexts.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows. Section 2 described the background and related work. Next, Section 3 presents the design and conduct of the Delphi study. The results are reported in Section 4 and synthesized into benefits, issues, risks, and mitigation strategies in Section 5. Subsequently, Section 6 discusses implications for research and industrial practice, followed by threats to validity in Section 7. Finally, Section 8 concludes the article.

2. Background & Related Work

The following paragraphs provide an overview of the technological structure, engineering and configuration characteristics, as well as adoption-related aspects of industrial AI systems.

2.1. Technological Structure of AI Systems

From a structural perspective, industrial AI systems in production can be described through multiple interconnected technological layers (Schuh and Scholz, 2019; Schuh et al., 2019, 2020) that we organize into three dimensions:

The application dimension describes the operational context of a system, including its working areas (e.g., predictive maintenance) and use cases (e.g., tool-wear prediction).

The physical dimension comprises machines (e.g., CNC machines) and processes (e.g., milling, sawing) that generate and execute operational data.

The cyber dimension contains the technological realization of the AI system itself, including data base (e.g., vibration, force strength, sound), learning strategies (e.g., supervised learning), tasks (e.g., classification), operations (e.g., neural networks), and their implementation infrastructures (e.g., AI development frameworks, programming languages) (Schuh et al., 2020; Scholz, 2022; May et al., 2023b).

This layered technological structure highlights that industrial AI systems are not limited to isolated machine-learning models, but emerge from interactions between operational environments and processes, hardware infrastructures, and data-driven software. Consequently, changes within individual technological layers may influence interconnected system components and operational production environments.

2.2. Engineering and Configuration of AI Systems

Industrial AI systems are commonly engineered along processing workflows that include data collection, pre-processing, learning, evaluation, and application (Goodfellow et al., 2016; Schuh et al., 2020). Data collection refers to acquiring operational and environmental data from

¹www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18912151

production environments (Wan et al., 2016), while pre-processing prepares and transforms data for subsequent analytical tasks with the goal of achieving the highest possible quality (Zhang et al., 2011, 2019). Learning describes the training of AI models based on prepared data (Goodfellow et al., 2016), while evaluation assesses the behavior and performance of the resulting model (Domingos, 2012; Schuh et al., 2020). Finally, application refers to integrating evaluated AI models into systemic production contexts (i.e., as AI systems) to generate actionable outputs that provide certain added value (Kusiak, 2018; Zhang et al., 2019).

In production environments, these steps do not occur in isolation, but depend on the configuration and integration of a variety of components, for example, industrial devices or sensors (Peres et al., 2020; Serôdio et al., 2024). Thus, engineering industrial AI systems requires coordinating AI-specific processing steps with the surrounding production infrastructure while considering dependencies between technological layers, parameter settings, data characteristics, and operational processes (Scholz, 2022; Hollender et al., 2024). This configurability introduces highly variable and interconnected system structures in which changes to individual components may affect related processes, interfaces, or system behavior (Binder et al., 2022; Mo et al., 2023; May and Adler, 2025).

2.3. Adoption of AI Systems

Besides challenges in engineering and configuring industrial AI systems, their adoption is strongly influenced by the expected operational and strategic implementation incentives within production environments (Monostori, 2014; Wang et al., 2018). At the operational level, AI systems are commonly associated with objectives such as improving system robustness, detecting anomalies, optimizing resource usage, or reducing downtime (Schuh and Scholz, 2019; May et al., 2023b; Ross et al., 2024). At the strategic level, organizations further aim to improve the central production objectives of cost efficiency, production time, and product quality (Monostori, 2014; Wang et al., 2018; Plathottam et al., 2023). However, these objectives are closely interconnected and may introduce practical trade-offs during development and operation. For example, achieving high production quality together with short production times may increase operational or implementation costs, whereas strong cost reductions may negatively affect flexibility or quality requirements (Bolstorff and Rosenbaum, 2007; Orm and Jeunet, 2018). Consequently, the perceived added value of industrial AI systems represents both a major adoption incentive and a practical operational challenge in production environments (Elahi et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2023).

2.4. Related Work

Research on industrial AI systems covers a broad range of technological and organizational topics within production environments. Prior studies investigate, for example, industrial AI application (Hou et al., 2017) and use case scenarios (Soori et al., 2023), key enabling technologies (Xi-ang et al., 2023), changes in operational processes (Mithas

et al., 2022), or cost-effectiveness (Soldatos, 2024). Additional work further discusses concepts related to engineering and configuring AI systems, including research on software engineering practices in AI system development (Gopinathan, 2025), architecture frameworks for human-AI teaming (Haindl et al., 2022), configurability in sustainable manufacturing (Todescato et al., 2023), or self-configuring industrial AI systems (Rehman et al., 2021).

We acknowledge that compared to the vast amount of theoretical research there is a quite limited number of literature involving practitioner or even expert voices. Using semi-structured interviews with industrial practitioners, Kutz et al. (2022) identified practical challenges related to AI system implementation, particularly regarding data quality, operational integration, and stakeholder involvement. Alon et al. (2025) reviewed Delphi studies on AI published during the last decade, including insights on the increasing integration of AI in manufacturing. Further, Van Dyck et al. (2023) focused on a future-oriented assessment of digital twins with consideration of AI potentials. Demlehner et al. (2021) applied a Delphi study in the automotive manufacturing domain to determine promising industrial AI application scenarios and implementation potentials. Similarly, Culot et al. (2020) used a Delphi-based approach with participants from research and industry to analyze expected opportunities and barriers associated with Industry 4.0 technologies, including AI systems.

We argue that existing studies often focus on specific fields within a domain, isolated organizational aspects, or selected adoption-related topics. The closest work to our study is our previous survey on AI system development and added value perception (May et al., 2025), which is based on a subset of the first-round responses of the present Delphi study. This earlier work primarily investigated development-related challenges and perceived added value of AI systems in production environments.

In contrast to existing work, the presented Delphi study explicitly incorporates configuration-related perspectives as an increasingly relevant topic in addition to development and added value aspects. To achieve this, we use a multi-round Delphi study to systematically analyze and reassess practical experiences of industrial AI experts to synthesize them in the context of benefits, issues, risks, and handling strategies in the context of industrial AI systems. Through this iterative consolidation process, the study contributes consolidated practitioner-oriented insights into established and emerging challenges associated with industrial AI systems in production environments.

3. Method

To systematically collect expert perspectives, we designed a *Delphi study* oriented towards Hsu and Sandford (2007). The study aimed to capture experiences in developing industrial AI systems, supporting the synthesis of typical

Figure 1: Overview of the Delphi-study design and process, including preparation, four Delphi rounds (n =participants; RR=Return Rate), processing and analysis, as well as concluding and reporting.

benefits, issues, risks, and mitigation strategies. Delphi studies provide a structured mechanism for collecting and refining expert knowledge in domains where consolidated empirical evidence is still scarce. Instead of relying on single-time observations (e.g., survey), the Delphi method collects insights over multiple iterations, refining them through repeated survey rounds combined with controlled feedback. This structured process allows participants to reconsider their perspectives in light of aggregated responses, which supports the gradual emergence of shared assessments and (possible) consensus across the expert panel (Hsu and Sandford, 2007; Vernon, 2009). We emphasize that the Delphi method is particularly useful for technologically complex domains, in our case industrial AI systems in production, where practical experience from practitioners represents a valuable source of knowledge. Note that across rounds, aggregated feedback from the previous iteration was provided to participants to support reflection and potential reconsideration of their responses (Hsu and Sandford, 2007).

3.1. Delphi-Study Design

Overall, we followed a four-phase study process, including (1) preparatory phase, (2) Delphi rounds, (3) data processing and analysis, (4) concluding and reporting (cf. Figure 1).

Preparation. In this phase, the first round questionnaire was designed. This questionnaire and all questionnaires of the subsequent round were developed using the online-survey tool Microsoft Forms, which enabled efficient distribution of the questionnaires, structured data collection, and centralized response management. In total, the first questionnaire consisted of 18 questions. Excluding demographics, the first questionnaire comprised 49 initial items. In our study, *items* denote the individual elements presented to the experts for evaluation, for example, including statements assessed via rating scales as well as options considered in ranking questions. Overall, the questions were distinguished into four thematic sections:

Section 1 – demographics: The first section gathered basic participant characteristics through three questions. These covered Q_1 years of experience in developing AI systems

(single choice), Q_2 industry background (multiple choice, including *prefer not to say* option), and Q_3 employment role (multiple choice). Participants were also asked to create an individual pseudonym that allowed responses to be linked across the Delphi rounds while maintaining privacy. The individual pseudonyms were created using the last letter of the birth month, the second letter of the mother's first name, and the first two letters of the birthplace. In all subsequent rounds, demographics were not requested again; instead, the previously generated pseudonyms were used exclusively to associate responses with the same participant.

Section 2 – development: The second section (ten items) focused on development-related aspects of AI systems and consisted of three questions. These addressed Q_4 the development phases perceived as most challenging (ranking), Q_5 key development-related issues encountered in practice (free text), and Q_6 typical strategies used to address or mitigate these issues (free text).

Section 3 – configurability: The third section (26 items) referred to practical aspects related to configuring AI systems, containing eight questions. Participants were asked to evaluate Q_7 the awareness of configurability of AI systems (Likert scale). Subsequent questions explored Q_8 frequently observed configuration issues (multiple choice), Q_9 whether these issues mainly stem from the AI systems themselves or from interacting systems (single choice), Q_{10} how often configuration problems occur in practice (Likert scale), and Q_{11} the impact of configuration decisions (multiple choice). Additional questions focused on Q_{12} typical domains or working areas in which configuration activities take place (free text), Q_{13} how configuration practices differ between traditional software systems and AI systems (free text), and Q_{14} strategies commonly applied to mitigate configuration issues (multiple choice). Note that all multiple-choice questions offered an additional *other* option, allowing participants to complement predefined answers with further explanations in free text.

Section 4 – experiences: In the fourth section (13 items), we collected practitioners' experiences with the AI system with which they had the greatest personal involvement in their

Table 1

Overview of the Delphi study questionnaire for round 2 (n=24), round 3 (n=22), and round 4 (n=21), focusing on development and configurability questions.

section	ID	question	answer options
development	Q ₄	Please rank the AIS development phases according to how challenging they are.	data preparation; design; implementation; deployment, operation; testing; change management
	Q ₅	Please rank the most important challenges that arise in the development or use of AIS according to their relevance.	data quality; system configurability; system adaptability/change management; meeting stakeholder expectations; model efficiency; system scalability; data handling/processing
	Q ₆	Please rank the most important challenges that arise in the development or use of AIS according to their relevance.	regular dataset testing; system templates; communication; improving data quality; iterative system optimization; holistic requirements engineering
	–	Further comments	free text
configurability	Q ₇	Is there an awareness of AIS configurability and related issues in industry?	5-level Likert scale on agreement
	Q ₈	Please rank the most common configuration issues encountered when deploying machine learning models in industrial settings according to their relevance.	incorrect parameter settings; hard-ware-software mismatch; unwanted feature interactions; dependency issues; programming errors; version issues; high latency; scalability limitations; security limitations;
	Q ₉	Do configuration issues arise more within AIS themselves or in combination of AIS with other systems?	in combination with other systems
	Q ₁₀	How often do AIS-related configuration issues occur?	5-level Likert scale on frequency
	Q ₁₁	Please rank the typical impacts of configuration issues regarding the performance and reliability of AIS according to their relevance.	reduced accuracy; inconsistent outputs; increased downtime; computational inefficiency; system vulnerabilities; scalability issues
	Q ₁₂	Please rank the working areas where configuration issues are more prevalent in AIS according to their relevance.	feature-rich working areas; real time data working areas; security-critical working areas; monitoring systems; all working areas; less common working areas
	Q ₁₃	Please rank the differences of configuration issues between AIS and traditional software systems in industrial environments.	higher complexity; lack of legal standards; greater data dependence; usage of real time data; more challenging versioning/configuring; black-box characteristics; need for more parameters; more specific requirements
	Q ₁₄	Please rank the most important solutions to overcome configuration issues in AIS according to their relevance.	hyperparameter optimization; regular testing; data as code approach; iterative development; reducing system variability; continuous monitoring; configuration-management tools
–	Further comments	free text	

organization, assuming that this system reflects their most substantial practical experience. Here, the broader goal was to consolidate these insights after analysis and generalize them into statements for evaluation in the subsequent Delphi rounds. Participants first reported **Q₁₅** the system's primary use case (single choice) and **Q₁₆** the learning strategy applied (single choice), both including an *other* option to allow additional entries. Then, they were asked to describe **Q₁₇** the main incentives for introducing this system in their organization (free text). Finally, participants evaluated **Q₁₈**

whether the implementation was considered economically worthwhile (Likert scale).

Delphi rounds. The iterative Delphi process constituted the second step of the study. All questionnaires were made accessible via Microsoft Forms, with participants receiving an invitation link by email for each round. In total After the first round, all open-ended responses were systematically analyzed and organized (cf. data processing and analysis). This method allowed us to synthesize the collected free-text statements into a structured set of items that served as the basis for subsequent evaluations. Then, participants

were asked to rank or assess these categories in the following rounds. Questions that had originally been formulated as rating items, such as those addressing the frequency of configuration issues, remained in their original Likert-scale format. Across rounds, participants were additionally encouraged to provide comments and reflections for each thematic block, namely *development*, *configurability*, and *trends* (created out of *experiences*). The overall questionnaire structure remained stable throughout the second, third, and fourth rounds, i.e., it consisted of the same set of 13 core questions to support comparability across these rounds. Naturally, wording and presentation of individual items and item orders were adapted based on results obtained from the previous round.

Processing and analysis. As the third step of the study, the collected responses were reviewed and analyzed by RM, HH, and MTS after each Delphi round. As an initial step, all submissions were screened to ensure completeness and sufficient response quality.

Quantitative analysis: Quantitative responses were analyzed using commonly applied procedures for Delphi studies. For questions requiring the ranking of items, we applied Kendall's coefficient of concordance (W) to assess the degree of agreement among participants regarding the relative ordering of items (Diamond et al., 2014). Kendall's W reflects how consistently participants assign similar ranks to the same set of items and ranges from 0 (no agreement) to 1 (perfect agreement). Values above 0.7 are typically interpreted as strong agreement among participants (Schmidt, 1997). To ensure statistical robustness, we considered results meaningful only when the associated significance level satisfied $p < 0.05$. For rating questions based on five-point Likert scales, responses were coded numerically from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*). Then, the interquartile range (IQR) was used to measure the distribution of responses (Von Der Gracht, 2012).

Qualitative analysis: Free-text responses were reviewed after each round by RM, HH, and MTS and analyzed using thematic analysis (Clarke and Braun, 2017), supported by open-card sorting to structure emerging themes (Zimmermann, 2016). After familiarizing with the responses, HH and MTS jointly coded the data, while RM conducted an independent coding of the same responses. The coding results were subsequently compared and discussed among these authors until agreement was reached. Based on this process, items were either retained as originally formulated, content-wise revised, or grouped into new themes. These themes were subsequently incorporated into the questionnaire of the following round or, in the case of the final round, used as the basis for the interpretation of the results.

Consensus: Consensus among participants was primarily assessed using the percentage of agreement, adopting a commonly reported threshold of 75% as an indication of agreement in Delphi studies (Diamond et al., 2014). For rating questions, consensus was additionally evaluated using

the IQR. Lower IQR values indicate a stronger convergence of opinions among participants. Following common recommendations, we interpreted $IQR \leq 0.5$ as evidence of consensus (Von Der Gracht, 2012; Diamond et al., 2014).

Stability: Building on recommendations for assessing stability in Delphi studies summarized by Von Der Gracht (2012), we defined thresholds to evaluate stability between Delphi rounds. For ranking questions, stability was assessed by comparing the percentage of participants assigning the same rank to an item between rounds. For categorical questions (e.g., single-choice items), stability was assessed by comparing the percentage of participants selecting each option between rounds. Responses were considered stable when the change in these percentages was $\leq 15\%$. For rating questions based on a five-point Likert scale, stability was assessed by comparing the difference between the coded mean ratings of two rounds based on the numerical codings (cf. quantitative analysis). Responses were considered stable when this difference is ≤ 0.5 (i.e., half a Likert-scale category).

Stopping criteria: The primary stopping criterion of the study was a predefined number of Delphi rounds (Diamond et al., 2014). In our case, the process was planned to conclude after four rounds. However, additional rounds would have been considered if agreement had not yet been sufficiently established across the majority of items (Von Der Gracht, 2012; Diamond et al., 2014). Another stopping criterion concerned the participant dropout (Hoerger, 2010). For the dropout, we defined a threshold of more than 30% relative to the initial Delphi panel.

Concluding and Reporting. In the final phase of the study, the findings of all Delphi rounds, however, primarily focusing on the results of round 4, were systematically concluded and reported by RM. More specifically, we reported following the Conducting and REporting of DELphi Studies (CREDES) guidelines proposed by Jünger et al. (2017). Although originally described for healthcare research, the reporting principles are not domain specific. Thus, we adopted the relevant elements and applied them to the context of industrial AI systems. To further support transparency and reproducibility, all collected data and the CREDES document are provided in an open-access repository.

3.2. Study Conduct

Participants. For panel size, we aimed to recruit 15 to 20 participants, which is commonly recommended for Delphi studies to obtain robust insights (McMillan et al., 2016; Belton et al., 2021). We recruited only participants who actively work in the field of AI systems, such as programmers, data scientists, or AI-system operators. The targeted working area was the production industry. We relied on four separate channels to reach potential participants:

1. a manually created mailing list (89 persons)
2. the professional network of the authors
3. the LinkedIn network of RM

Table 2

Response overview of the demographics across all Delphi rounds. Values are reported as n (%). Percentages may exceed 100% due to multiple selections.

question	options	round 1	round 2	round 3	round 4
Q ₁ : experience	0 to 2	2 (8%)	1 (4%)	1 (5%)	1 (5%)
	3 to 5	7 (27%)	6 (25%)	6 (27%)	6 (29%)
	6 to 10	7 (27%)	7 (29%)	5 (23%)	5 (24%)
	11+	10 (39%)	10 (42%)	10 (45%)	9 (43%)
Q ₂ : industry	manufacturing	20 (77%)	19 (79%)	17 (77%)	16 (76%)
	information technology	14 (54%)	14 (58%)	13 (59%)	13 (62%)
	research	10 (39%)	10 (42%)	10 (45%)	9 (43%)
	logistics	3 (12%)	2 (8%)	2 (9%)	2 (10%)
	prefer not to say	1 (4%)	1 (4%)	1 (5%)	1 (5%)
Q ₃ : employment	research & development	23 (87%)	22 (92%)	20 (91%)	19 (90%)
	operations	11 (42%)	9 (38%)	8 (36%)	8 (38%)
	quality	3 (12%)	3 (13%)	3 (14%)	3 (14%)
	management	2 (8%)	1 (4%)	1 (5%)	1 (5%)
	other	2 (8%)	2 (8%)	2 (9%)	2 (10%)

4. snowballing via participant networks

Delphi Process. Using the defined recruitment channels, we reached at least 94 potential participants; however, the exact number of persons approached via LinkedIn and snowball sampling remains unknown. The first Delphi round was conducted from May 22 to June 22, 2024 (i.e., four weeks) and yielded 27 responses in total and 26 valid responses after data cleaning. All subsequent rounds were open for two weeks, with a cooling period of two weeks between consecutive rounds. Round 2 involved 24 participants (return rate 92%), followed by 22 participants in round 3 (return rate 92%). A fourth round was conducted from September 29 to October 12, 2025, after an intentionally longer interval of approximately one year. This round again allowed two weeks for participation and resulted in 21 participants (return rate 96%). The extended pause was introduced to examine the stability of expert assessments over time and to identify potential shifts in priorities after a prolonged reflection period.

The questionnaire was iteratively refined across the Delphi rounds. Round 1 included 49 items. For round 2, eleven items were removed and 42 new items were added based on expert responses. Precisely, in the *development* section, one item was removed and 13 added, while 19 items were added in the *configurability* section. In the *experiences* section, all initial items were replaced by ten new items (i.e., statements), also changing its title to *adoption*. In rounds 3 and 4, no further items were added or removed; only the ordering of options in ranking questions was adjusted based on the previous round's results.

4. Results

In the following, we present the results of our Delphi study, focusing on *demographics*, *development*, *configurability*, and *adoption* (called *experiences* in round 1). While demographics are reported across all rounds, the analysis of

the remaining topics focuses on the final outcomes of round 4. Data from the earlier rounds are available in our open-access repository. Except for the demographics, we report the agreement (%) for each item. Note that the IQR remained 0 for all rating questions.

4.1. Demographics

In Table 2, we show an overview of the Demographics. Generally, our panel reflected a high level of Q₁ professional experience in AI-system development. Across the rounds, between 66–67% of the experts reported more than six years of experience. Only around 6% have zero to two years of experience. Most respondents reported their Q₂ industry backgrounds in the manufacturing sector (77–79%) and information technology (54–62%), while smaller shares indicated affiliations with research (39–45%) and logistics (8–12%). One participant selected the *prefer not to say* option. In terms of Q₃ employment roles, research and development positions were most common among the panel (87–92%). Further roles referred to operations (36–42%), quality management (12–14%), general management (4–8%), and other (8–10%), including, for example, risk management. Note that all participants included in our study are from Germany.

Based on the characteristics described, our expert panel can be regarded as well aligned with the focus of this study. At the same time, the number of participants remained largely stable throughout the Delphi process and, even in the round 4, slightly exceeded the panel sizes commonly reported for specialized Delphi studies (cf. Section 3.2). We emphasize that these factors support a high level of confidence in the relevance and reliability of the collected assessments.

4.2. Development

As shown in Figure 2, participants identified data preparation (95%) as the most Q₄ challenging development phase of AI systems ($W = 0.96$). Deployment (100%), operation

Figure 2: Ranking of development phases (Q_4) and development-related challenges (Q_5) in round 4. Lower mean ranks indicate higher relevance. Light gray bars indicate unstable rankings.

(76%), and change management (81%) followed, whereas testing (95%), design (91%), and implementation (91%) generally received lower ranks (all stable). Data quality (100%) was clearly perceived as the most Q_5 critical development challenge ($W = 0.99$). The following challenges referred to system customization and configurability (100%), system adaptability and change management (100%), meeting stakeholder expectations (100%), and model efficiency (100%). Besides system scalability (71%) and data handling (71%), which were considered less critical overall, all other items remained stable. Interestingly, the perceived importance of these two fluctuated across rounds, as some participants continued to interchange their positions until the final round. Regarding Q_6 handling strategies ($W = 0.96$), regular testing (100%) and the use of AI-system templates (100%) were most frequently considered appropriate strategies. Stakeholder communication (81%) and improvements in data quality (81%) followed as additional, stable strategies. Iterative system optimization (71%) and holistic requirements-engineering processes (71%) were ranked lowest and remained unstable until the final round. Ten experts provided additional comments. Specifically, they mentioned the importance of AI explainability and traceability (2), compliance with new legal regulations (2), and integration of different AI technologies (2). Other comments concerned AI-system templates (1), organizational readiness (1), pre-processing effort (1), and limited training data (1).

4.3. Configurability

Responses regarding the Q_7 awareness of configurability in AI systems indicate stable consensus that most participants selected the neutral option, with 95% neither agreeing nor disagreeing; 5% agreed. Referring to typical Q_8 configuration issues (cf. Figure 3), all opinions remained stable with versioning issues most frequently selected at the first rank (100%). Dependency issues (95%) and scalability limitations (95%) followed. Less relevant issues were ranked as following (stable): unwanted feature interactions (100%),

incorrect parameter configurations (100%), mismatches between hardware and software components (100%), programming errors (86%), high latency (86%), and security limitations in the target infrastructure (100%). Related to Q_9 ($W = 0.99$), the results show that configuration issues occur primarily when AI systems interact with other systems rather than within AI systems themselves (100%). Moreover, in the context of Q_{10} configuration-issue occurrences, all responses indicate that these occur frequently (100%, stable). Regarding the Q_{11} impacts of configuration issues ($W = 0.97$), all participants agreed on increased downtime as most prominent impact (100%). As illustrated in Figure 3, the remaining impacts were ranked as follows: scalability limitations (86%), inconsistent system outputs (67%), system vulnerabilities (81%), computational inefficiency (100%), and reduced accuracy (100%). Besides inconsistent system outputs, all items were stable. The responses on the Q_{12} working areas ($W = 0.98$) were all stable and showed that most participants ranked working environments characterized by high feature-richness as most dominant area in the context of configuration issues (100%). It is followed by areas relying on real-time data (81%), monitoring systems (81%), not-specified areas (100%), areas with increasing security requirements (100%), and areas in which AI systems are still uncommon (100%). The Q_{13} differences between AI systems and traditional cyber physical systems ($W = 0.98$) were ranked as follows (stable): higher system complexity (100%), use of real-time data (91%), greater data dependence (100%), more challenging versioning and configuring (91%), need for more parameters (91%), more specific infrastructure requirements (91%), missing legal standards (100%), and black-box characteristics (100%). The participants ranked in the context of Q_{14} mitigation strategies to address configuration issues ($W = 0.93$) regular testing (100%) first, followed by continuous monitoring (91%) and the use of configuration-management tools (71%, unstable). These were followed by reducing system variability (71%, unstable), data-as-code approaches (91%), hyperparameter

Development of Industrial Artificial-Intelligence Systems: A Delphi Study

Figure 3: Ranking of configuration issues (Q_8) and configuration issue impacts (Q_{11}) in round 4. Lower mean ranks indicate higher relevance. Light gray bars indicate unstable rankings.

Table 3

Assessments of adoption statements regarding industrial AI-system practice as well as operational and economic benefits, including ratings, agreement levels, and stability in Delphi round 4.

item	rating	n (%)	consensus	stability
industrial AI-system practice				
Supervised learning is currently the most popular learning strategy for industrial environments.	agree	21 (100%)	yes	yes
The prediction of machine or component failures is currently one of the most popular use cases for industrial AI systems.	agree/disagree	17 (81%)	yes	yes
operational benefits				
AI systems enhance the decision-making capabilities in industrial sectors.	agree	18 (86%)	yes	yes
A main reason for the implementation of AI systems is to improve operational efficiency.	agree	18 (86%)	yes	yes
A main reason for the implementation of AI systems is to reduce the downtime in industrial environments.	agree	17 (81%)	yes	yes
The implementation of AI systems typically leads to an increase in production capacity and a reduction in manual labor.	agree	21 (100%)	yes	yes
The implementation of AI systems improves the overall efficiency in engineering tasks (i.e., planning, production, and maintenance).	agree	18 (86%)	yes	yes
A main reason for the implementation of AI systems is their positive impact on production quality.	agree/disagree	19 (90%)	yes	yes
economic benefits				
A main reason for the implementation of AI systems is to save costs.	agree	18 (86%)	yes	yes
The implementation of AI systems is typically worthwhile from an economic point of view.	agree	20 (95%)	yes	yes

optimization (100%), and iterative development practices (100%). Additionally, we got further comments from 17 experts. They mentioned dependency hell (5), combinatorial explosion (5), configuration reproducibility and feature traceability (4), versioning issues (3), parameter variability (2), misconfigurations (2) and operator fatigue (1).

4.4. Adoption

Out of the experiences (round 1), we derived ten statements to be assessed by the experts. In Table 3, all items and their assessments are presented. Eight items reached agreement while the participants neither agreed nor disagreed with two items. Each item reached stable consensus.

Further comments concerned system integration (4), learning strategies (2), data infrastructures (2), architectures and configurability (2), human and explainability aspects (2), and system lifecycle management (1).

5. Thematic Synthesis

By synthesizing the data retrieved from the questionnaire responses, we derived recurring themes related to **benefits**, **issues**, **risks**, and **mitigation strategies** that are currently part of the daily business practice of our experts.

5.1. Benefits

Operational and Economic Enablement. Industrial AI systems are perceived as operational and organizational enablers rather than isolated analytical models (Zdravković et al., 2021). Experts associated AI systems with improved operational efficiency, reduced downtime, increased production capacity, lower manual effort, and improved engineering processes. In addition, the findings imply that industrial AI systems are generally perceived as economically worthwhile and beneficial for production quality, which is already highlighted by a variety of research (Elahi et al., 2023; Plathottam et al., 2023). Altogether, these findings indicate that the practical value of AI systems is primarily associated with measurable operational improvements and economic optimization within industrial environments.

Infrastructure-Level Integration and Scalability. There is a clear transition from isolated AI pilots toward integrated and scalable production infrastructures. Experts repeatedly highlighted the importance of modular architectures, configurable components, standardized data infrastructures, and unified data models for deploying AI systems across heterogeneous production environments. Furthermore, the integration of AI capabilities into existing operational systems such as maintenance, quality management, and manufacturing execution system platforms (Rakholia et al., 2024; Lin, 2024) was perceived as important. Hence, perceived benefits emerge not only from individual AI models, but also from their integration into larger operational ecosystems and smart factory architectures.

Human-Centered Decision Support. While automation remains an important objective, experts perceive AI systems as supporting rather than replacing human operators. This opinion is also reflected by recent research (Rakholia et al., 2024; Tarafdar, 2025). In particular, explainability and interpretability (Arrieta et al., 2020) were emphasized, especially in safety-relevant production environments where operators must understand system behavior and decision processes. These capabilities are essential for validating AI-generated recommendations, understanding unexpected system behavior, and maintaining confidence in operational decisions. Thus, successful industrial AI adoption depends not only on automation capabilities but also on the ability of operators to understand, supervise, and effectively integrate AI-supported decisions into existing production processes.

5.2. Issues

Integration and Infrastructure Complexity. A major issue of industrial AI systems concerns their integration into heterogeneous production and automation environments. Experts emphasized difficulties related to legacy infrastructures, proprietary communication protocols, and the integration of AI capabilities into existing operational systems. In particular, the combination of multiple AI modules, automation technologies, and heterogeneous runtime environments was associated with increasing system complexity and unexpected side effects. Furthermore, the results imply that many industrial AI initiatives fail not because of insufficient model capabilities, but because of challenges related to operational integration and infrastructure compatibility. Therefore, integration complexity represents a central practical barrier for industrial AI deployment in real-world production environments (Kutz et al., 2022; Sinha and Lee, 2024).

Configuration Complexity. Another issue concerns the increasing configuration and variability complexity of industrial AI systems (Peres et al., 2020; Rabiser and Zoitl, 2021; Sinha and Lee, 2024). The quantitative findings already highlighted configurability, adaptability, and deployment as major challenges. These findings were strongly reinforced by the qualitative statements, where experts referred to dependency hell (Boué et al., 2023), hidden dependencies (Nyakundi, 2026), parameter variability (Eggenesperger et al., 2019), combinatorial explosion (Fortz, 2023), and configuration mismatches between training and production environments (Rahman et al., 2025). In addition, experts highlighted that variability is frequently tolerated rather than systematically engineered, resulting in fragile dependencies and unstable system behavior across different production settings. In addition, the complexity of industrial AI systems extends beyond the configuration of individual models or software components. Since configuration decisions frequently affect multiple system dimensions and layers simultaneously (cf. Section 2.1), dependencies can propagate across technological boundaries and create unforeseen interactions. As a result, local configuration changes may also trigger system-wide effects that are difficult to predict, validate, and manage throughout the system lifecycle.

Data and Lifecycle Management Challenges. The findings further show substantial challenges related to data management, traceability, and lifecycle control. Experts described high efforts for cleaning, synchronizing, and contextualizing industrial data, as well as limitations caused by missing labeled failure events. At the same time, reproducibility, versioning, and configuration traceability were described as difficult and often associated with unclear or highly manual workflows (Semmelrock et al., 2025). Several experts additionally emphasized growing requirements for long-term lifecycle management, including monitoring, retraining strategies, and configuration management. In general, the operation of industrial AI systems increasingly requires continuous lifecycle-oriented management processes that extend far beyond initial model development.

Organizational and Governance Limitations. The results show that organizational readiness and governance capabilities represent important practical limitations for industrial AI adoption (Kinkel et al., 2022). Experts reported that many organizations, including small and medium-sized companies, lack sufficient resources, validation procedures, and operational structures for deploying and maintaining industrial AI systems at scale. Furthermore, increasing regulatory requirements (e.g., EU AI Act) were frequently perceived as difficult to operationalize due to limited guidance and unclear implementation strategies. The findings therefore suggest that barriers to industrial AI adoption often arise from missing organizational capabilities and governance structures rather than from limitations of the AI technologies themselves.

5.3. Risks

Operational Risks. The findings indicate that unresolved configuration, integration, and deployment issues can directly threaten operational stability within industrial environments. The quantitative results already identified increased downtime, scalability issues, and inconsistent outputs as major consequences of configuration-related problems, which are widely known issues in research (Xu and Zhou, 2015; Rahman et al., 2025). These findings were reinforced by qualitative expert statements describing degraded model performance, configuration mismatches between training and production environments, and even complete machine stops after deployment errors. In addition, experts repeatedly emphasized that hidden dependencies and combinatorial interactions between models, data sources, and runtime components create fragile operational environments with difficult-to-predict system behavior. Thus, our findings imply that industrial AI systems increasingly introduce risks related to operational instability and production disruptions in heterogeneous production infrastructures.

Transparency and Control Risks. A major risk concerns the increasing loss of transparency, traceability, and controllability of industrial AI systems (Kroll, 2021; Mora-Cantallops et al., 2021). Several times, experts stated explainability, traceability, and documentation as critical requirements, particularly in safety-relevant production environments. At the same time, the findings revealed substantial difficulties regarding versioning, reproducibility, and configuration tracking. The growing variability of configurations, parameters, models, and deployment environments further amplifies these challenges. As a result, organizations may struggle to understand which configuration states, model versions, or dependencies are responsible for specific system behaviors. Altogether, the findings indicate that industrial AI systems risk evolving into both difficult-to-trace and difficult-to-control operational ecosystems.

Human and Organizational Risks. There are several human-centered and organizational risks associated with industrial AI adoption, which are related to the already described

issues. Experts highlighted that frequent configuration problems and false alarms may lead to operator fatigue (Rožanec et al., 2023) and reduced trust (Dorton and Harper, 2022) in AI-supported processes. Furthermore, insufficient explainability may limit operator acceptance and reduce confidence in safety-relevant decision support systems (Arrieta et al., 2020). The findings also indicate that many organizations still lack sufficient validation capabilities, governance structures, and operational readiness for deploying AI systems at scale (Uren and Edwards, 2023; Hussein et al., 2026). Consequently, we state that industrial AI risks increasingly emerge not only from technical failures, but also from organizational limitations and human operational factors.

Governance and Compliance Risks. Our findings also indicate growing governance and compliance risks associated with industrial AI systems. As already stated, experts referred to increasing regulatory pressure, leading to high risks regarding successful AI system implementation. In fact, risks may also arise in other regulatory areas, including security (ISO/IEC 27000). In particular, security incidents in safety-critical areas may have severe consequences, as security breaches may compromise system functionality, potentially causing environmental damage and endangering human lives (May et al., 2023a, 2024a,b). However, integrating security comes with huge challenges, such as considering increasing system complexity due to growing configuration spaces (Mellado et al., 2010; Varela-Vaca et al., 2021). Consequently, increasing configurability and operational integration can make industrial AI systems more difficult to govern, audit, and secure. This challenge is further amplified when configuration decisions, model versions, and system dependencies are insufficiently documented or traceable, limiting organizations' ability to demonstrate compliance and maintain operational control.

5.4. Mitigation Strategies

Standardization and Modularization. Standardization and modularization represent central mitigation strategies for managing the growing complexity of industrial AI systems. Modular architectures and components (Pfeiffer et al., 2023), reusable templates (May et al., 2023b), and standardized data infrastructures (Liang et al., 2022) are important approaches for improving scalability and operational integration. In particular, unified data models and reusable parameter configurations were perceived as important mechanisms for reducing integration effort and configuration inconsistencies across heterogeneous production environments.

Traceability and Lifecycle Management. Another mitigation strategy concerns the establishment of traceability and lifecycle-oriented management practices, which are ongoing challenges at the same time. Concrete approaches concerned tagging mechanisms, unique identifiers, configuration tracking, versioning approaches, and monitoring processes as important measures for improving reproducibility and operational transparency (Mora-Cantallops et al., 2021; Schlegel and Sattler, 2023). In addition, several statements

emphasized the growing importance of lifecycle management strategies (Kreuzberger et al., 2023) including retraining processes, drift monitoring, and continuous configuration management. To conclude, the results suggest that effective operation of industrial AI systems depends on the ability to continuously track configurations, model versions, data changes, and system behavior throughout the system lifecycle. Without such traceability mechanisms, organizations may struggle to reproduce results, diagnose failures, or manage the evolution of deployed AI systems.

Transparency and Operational Oversight. Transparency and operational oversight are essential mitigation strategies for industrial AI systems. Experts stated explainability, documentation, and traceability as prerequisites for understanding system behavior, diagnosing unexpected outcomes, and validating AI-supported decisions (Arrieta et al., 2020; Tarafdar, 2025). In particular, these practices become increasingly important in safety-relevant production environments, where operators remain responsible for assessing and acting upon AI-generated recommendations.

Governance and Structured Reuse. Governance frameworks and organizational capability development are also relevant from the experts' perspective. While regulatory frameworks and standards can lead to issues and risks, they are also a chance for structuring industrial AI governance and operational control (Agarwal and Nene, 2024; Saleh and Abdulsalam, 2025). Investing in standardized infrastructures based on core assets (e.g., templates) and the subsequent derivation of configured variants can lead to several advantages, including systematic reuse, improved quality assurance, or reduced engineering effort (Apel et al., 2013; Rabiser and Zoitl, 2021; May and Adler, 2025). We argue that effective mitigation requires not only technical solutions, but also structured governance mechanisms, standardized engineering practices, and systematic reuse strategies.

6. Implications

To make the insights we described more actionable, we provide additional implications for both research and practice based on them.

Research implications. For researchers, the findings suggest that future work should move beyond isolated model evaluations and place greater emphasis on the engineering and operation of industrial AI systems in production environments. Research should investigate how industrial AI systems can be engineered as configurable software ecosystems through systematic variability management, reusable core assets, and configurable platform architectures. In particular, approaches originating from software product line engineering (Apel et al., 2013), such as reusable core assets, templates, reference architectures, and configurable variants, appear promising for improving scalability, maintainability, and systematic reuse in industrial AI environments. Future studies should therefore complement performance metrics

with operational qualities, such as configurability, maintainability, traceability, or reproducibility.

Practical implications. For practitioners, the findings indicate that investments should primarily target operational and organizational capabilities rather than model development alone. Organizations should establish reusable AI platforms based on standardized architectures, templates, and configurable core assets that support the systematic derivation of AI system variants for different production contexts. Here, we recommend to take product line engineering approaches (Apel et al., 2013) into account. Such approaches can reduce engineering effort, improve consistency, facilitate traceability, and support the scalable deployment and maintenance of industrial AI systems across heterogeneous environments. Finally, organizations should complement these technical capabilities with structured governance mechanisms, including lifecycle management, configuration management, and clear ownership of models, data assets, and configurations, to maintain operational control and long-term system reliability.

7. Threats to Validity

Next, we describe relevant threats to the internal, external, and construct validity of our study.

7.1. Internal Validity

Internal validity may be influenced by researcher interpretation during the analysis and consolidation of qualitative responses. Free-text responses from the initial Delphi rounds were analyzed using thematic analysis and open-card sorting, which required us to interpret and group statements into themes and structured items. Furthermore, the final synthesis of qualitative feedback after round 4 may introduce subjective bias. To mitigate these threats, responses were independently reviewed and coded by multiple researchers and discussed until consensus was reached. The general robustness of our results is supported by the stability of the consensus process. In the final round, agreement levels were high ($W > 0.93$) with statistically significant results ($p < 0.001$), indicating a strong and reliable convergence of expert opinions that transcends individual round-to-round fluctuations. Nevertheless, another primary threat relates to the iterative nature of the Delphi process. Participants received aggregated feedback, which might trigger a bandwagon effect where experts align their assessments with emerging group tendencies rather than maintaining their initial perspectives (Bhandari and Hallowell, 2021).

7.2. External Validity

The generalizability of the findings is limited by the specific study context. The Delphi panel consisted exclusively of experts involved in developing or operating industrial AI systems. While this focus ensured practical expertise, the results may not directly transfer to other AI domains, e.g., healthcare. Additionally, the recruitment strategy may have introduced selection bias, as practitioners already connected

to these professional networks might be more inclined to participate. The panel size, however, supports the external validity within the industrial domain. Starting with 26 valid participants and maintaining high return rates (cf. Figure 1) aligns with established recommendations for Delphi studies in specialized fields (McMillan et al., 2016; Belton et al., 2021). Despite this, a potential social-desirability bias remains, as participants might report practices that align with organizational expectations rather than actual daily-business operations.

7.3. Construct Validity

Construct validity concerns whether the questionnaire items adequately represent the complex concepts of industrial AI systems. A primary threat arises from the diverse backgrounds of the practitioners; different technical roles and responsibilities can lead to varying interpretations of terms like *development challenges* or *configuration issues*. So, participants may interpret individual items differently despite identical formulations and explanations from our site. Furthermore, the operationalization of these socio-technical concepts into discrete items may not fully capture the entire depth of real-world industrial practice. To address this issue, the questionnaire was iteratively refined. Although removing or introducing items after the first round (Diamond et al., 2014) limits strict comparability between rounds, it ensures that the constructs measured are more accurately aligned with the actual experiences of the experts.

8. Conclusion

In this article, we presented a four-round Delphi study with 26 practitioners involved in the development, configuration, and operation of industrial AI systems in production environments. Using iterative expert assessments and thematic synthesis, the study consolidated practical experiences regarding benefits, issues, risks, and mitigation strategies associated with industrial AI systems.

The findings indicate that industrial AI systems are increasingly evolving from isolated analytical models toward integrated and highly configurable operational ecosystems. While experts strongly associated AI systems with operational efficiency, production optimization, and scalable infrastructures, they simultaneously emphasized substantial challenges related to integration complexity, variability, lifecycle management, traceability, and governance. In particular, dependency-related problems, configuration mismatches, and operational integration into heterogeneous environments emerged as recurring practical concerns.

Overall, the study suggests that many practical challenges of industrial AI systems no longer primarily emerge from model development itself, but from their operational embedding into highly configurable, socio-technical production environments. Thus, future research should focus on system-centric engineering perspectives, particularly regarding variability management, lifecycle governance, explainability, and operational integration of industrial AI systems.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank all experts who participated in this Delphi panel.

Declaration of Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Funding

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Data Availability

All data collected during this study is available via an open-access repository.

Declaration of Generative AI Use

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT 5.2 Pro in order to identify spelling and grammatical errors and to assist with paraphrasing. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Richard May: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision. **Leonard Cassel:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. **Hashir Hussain:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Muhammad Talha Siddiqui:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Tobias Niemand:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing. **Paul Scholz:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing. **Paul Scholz:** Writing - Review & Editing. **Thomas Leich:** Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration.

References

- Agarwal, A., Nene, M.J., 2024. Standardised schema and taxonomy for ai incident databases in critical digital infrastructure, in: Pune Section International Conference (PuneCon), IEEE. pp. 1–6.
- Alon, I., Haidar, H., Haidar, A., Guimon, J., 2025. The future of artificial intelligence: Insights from recent delphi studies. *Futures* 165, 103514.
- Apel, S., Batory, D., Kästner, C., Saake, G., 2013. Feature-oriented software product lines. Springer.
- Arrieta, A.B., Díaz-Rodríguez, N., Del Ser, J., Bennetot, A., Tabik, S., Barbado, A., García, S., Gil-López, S., Molina, D., Benjamins, R., et al., 2020. Explainable artificial intelligence (xai): Concepts, taxonomies, opportunities and challenges toward responsible ai. *Information Fusion* 58, 82–115.

- Belton, I., Wright, G., Sissons, A., Bolger, F., Crawford, M.M., Hamlin, I., Lūka, C.T.B., Vasilichi, A., 2021. Delphi with feedback of rationales: How large can a delphi group be such that participants are not overloaded, de-motivated, or disengaged? *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 170, 120897.
- Bhambri, P., Rani, S., Khang, A., 2024. Ai-driven digital twin and resource optimization in industry 4.0 ecosystem. *Intelligent Techniques for Predictive Data Analytics*, 47–69.
- Bhandari, S., Hallowell, M.R., 2021. Identifying and controlling biases in expert-opinion research: Guidelines for variations of delphi, nominal group technique, and focus groups. *Journal of Management in Engineering* 37, 04021015.
- Binder, C., Neureiter, C., Lüder, A., 2022. Towards a domain-specific information architecture enabling the investigation and optimization of flexible production systems by utilizing artificial intelligence. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 123, 49–81.
- Bolstorff, P., Rosenbaum, R., 2007. Supply chain excellence: A handbook for dramatic improvement using the scor model. *Journal of Supply Chain Management* 39, 38.
- Boué, L., Kunireddy, P., Subotić, P., 2023. Automatically resolving data source dependency hell in large scale data science projects, in: *International Conference on AI Engineering–Software Engineering for AI (CAIN)*, IEEE. pp. 1–6.
- Chryssolouris, G., Alexopoulos, K., Arkouli, Z., 2023. Artificial intelligence in manufacturing systems, in: *A Perspective on Artificial Intelligence in Manufacturing*. Springer, pp. 79–135.
- Clarke, V., Braun, V., 2017. Thematic analysis. *The journal of positive psychology* 12, 297–298.
- Culot, G., Orzes, G., Sartor, M., Nassimbeni, G., 2020. The future of manufacturing: A delphi-based scenario analysis on industry 4.0. *Technological forecasting and social change* 157, 120092.
- Demlehner, Q., Schoemer, D., Laumer, S., 2021. How can artificial intelligence enhance car manufacturing? a delphi study-based identification and assessment of general use cases. *International Journal of Information Management* 58, 102317.
- Diamond, I.R., Grant, R.C., Feldman, B.M., Pencharz, P.B., Ling, S.C., Moore, A.M., Wales, P.W., 2014. Defining consensus: A systematic review recommends methodologic criteria for reporting of delphi studies. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology* 67, 401–409.
- Domingos, P., 2012. A few useful things to know about machine learning. *Communications of the ACM* 55, 78–87.
- Dorton, S.L., Harper, S.B., 2022. A naturalistic investigation of trust, ai, and intelligence work. *Journal of Cognitive Engineering and Decision Making* 16, 222–236.
- Eggensperger, K., Lindauer, M., Hutter, F., 2019. Pitfalls and best practices in algorithm configuration. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research* 64, 861–893.
- Elahi, M., Afolaranmi, S.O., Martinez Lastra, J.L., Perez Garcia, J.A., 2023. A comprehensive literature review of the applications of ai techniques through the lifecycle of industrial equipment. *Discover artificial intelligence* 3, 43.
- EU AI Act, 2024. Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024. *Law. European Union (EU)*.
- Fortz, S., 2023. Variability-aware behavioural learning, in: *International Systems and Software Product Line Conference (SPLC)*, ACM. pp. 11–15.
- Goodfellow, I., Bengio, Y., Courville, A., Bengio, Y., 2016. *Deep learning*. volume 1. MIT Press.
- Gopinathan, V.R., 2025. Software engineering practices for ai-driven systems: From development to deployment (mlops perspective). *International Journal of Science, Research and Technology* 8, 13493–13500.
- Haindl, P., Buchgeher, G., Khan, M., Moser, B., 2022. Towards a reference software architecture for human-ai teaming in smart manufacturing, in: *International Conference on Software Engineering: New Ideas and Emerging Results (ICSE-NIER)*, ACM. pp. 96–100.
- Hoerger, M., 2010. Participant dropout as a function of survey length in internet-mediated university studies: implications for study design and voluntary participation in psychological research. *Cyberpsychology, behavior, and social networking* 13, 697–700.
- Hollender, M., Xu, C., Tan, R., 2024. Engineering challenges in industrial ai, in: *International Conference on AI Engineering-Software Engineering for AI (CAIN)*, ACM. pp. 41–42.
- Hou, B.C., Yu, W.T., Lu, X.B., Yang, C.w., et al., 2017. Applications of artificial intelligence in intelligent manufacturing: a review. *Frontiers of Information Technology & Electronic Engineering* 18, 86–96.
- Hsu, C.C., Sandford, B.A., 2007. The delphi technique: Making sense of consensus. *Practical Assessment, Research, and Evaluation* 12.
- Hussein, R., Zink, A., Ramadan, B., Howard, F.M., Hightower, M., Shah, S., Beaulieu-Jones, B.K., 2026. Advancing healthcare ai governance through a comprehensive maturity model based on systematic review. *NPJ Digital Medicine* 9, 236.
- ISO/IEC 27000, 2018. *ISO/IEC 27000:2018 – Information technology – Security techniques – Information security management systems – Overview and vocabulary*. Standard. International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC).
- Jünger, S., Payne, S.A., Brine, J., Radbruch, L., Brearley, S.G., 2017. Guidance on conducting and reporting delphi studies (credes) in palliative care: Recommendations based on a methodological systematic review. *Palliative Medicine* 31, 684–706.
- Khan, A.N., Jabeen, F., Mehmood, K., Soomro, M.A., Bresciani, S., 2023. Paving the way for technological innovation through adoption of artificial intelligence in conservative industries. *Journal of Business Research* 165, 114019.
- Khang, A., Abdullayev, V., Hahanov, V., Shah, V., 2024. *Advanced IoT technologies and applications in the industry 4.0 digital economy*. CRC Press.
- Kinkel, S., Baumgartner, M., Cherubini, E., 2022. Prerequisites for the adoption of ai technologies in manufacturing—evidence from a worldwide sample of manufacturing companies. *Technovation* 110, 102375.
- Kreuzberger, D., Kühl, N., Hirschl, S., 2023. Machine learning operations (mlops): Overview, definition, and architecture. *IEEE Access* 11, 31866–31879.
- Kroll, J.A., 2021. Outlining traceability: A principle for operationalizing accountability in computing systems, in: *Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT)*, ACM. pp. 758–771.
- Kusiak, A., 2018. Smart manufacturing. *International Journal of Production Research* 56, 508–517.
- Kutz, J., Neuhüttler, J., Spilski, J., Lachmann, T., 2022. Implementation of ai technologies in manufacturing—success factors and challenges. *The Human Side of Service Engineering* 62.
- Liang, W., Tadesse, G.A., Ho, D., Fei-Fei, L., Zaharia, M., Zhang, C., Zou, J., 2022. Advances, challenges and opportunities in creating data for trustworthy ai. *Nature Machine Intelligence* 4, 669–677.
- Lin, X., 2024. Artificial intelligence in the industrial engineering. *Advances in Operation Research and Production Management* 1, 1–6.
- May, R., Adler, S., 2025. Experiences in developing configurable digital twin-assisted xr applications for industrial environments, in: *Working Conference on Variability Modelling of Software-Intensive Systems (VaMoS)*, ACM. pp. 107–111.
- May, R., Alex, A.J., Suresh, R., Leich, T., 2024a. Product-line engineering for smart manufacturing: A systematic mapping study on security concepts, in: *International Conference on Software Technologies (ICSOFT)*, SciTePress. pp. 323–330.
- May, R., Cassel, L., Hussain, H., Siddiqui, M.T., Niemand, T., Scholz, P., Leich, T., 2025. Adopting artificial-intelligence systems in manufacturing: A practitioner survey on challenges and added value, in: *International Conference on Software Technologies (ICSOFT)*, SciTePress. pp. 87–98.
- May, R., Gautam, J., Sharma, C., Biermann, C., Leich, T., 2023a. A systematic mapping study on security in configurable safety-critical systems based on product-line concepts, in: *International Conference on Software Technologies (ICSOFT)*, SciTePress. pp. 217–224.
- May, R., Krüger, J., Leich, T., 2024b. Sok: How artificial-intelligence incidents can jeopardize safety and security, in: *International Conference*

- on Availability, Reliability and Security (ARES), ACM. pp. 1–12.
- May, R., Niemand, T., Scholz, P., Leich, T., 2023b. Design patterns for monitoring and prediction machine learning systems: Systematic literature review and cluster analysis. *ICSOF*, 209–216.
- McMillan, S.S., King, M., Tully, M.P., 2016. How to use the nominal group and delphi techniques. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy* 38, 655–662.
- Mellado, D., Fernández-Medina, E., Piattini, M., 2010. Security requirements engineering framework for software product lines. *Information and Software Technology* 52, 1094–1117.
- Mithas, S., Chen, Z.L., Saldanha, T.J., De Oliveira Silveira, A., 2022. How will artificial intelligence and industry 4.0 emerging technologies transform operations management? *Production and operations management* 31, 4475–4487.
- Mo, F., Rehman, H.U., Monetti, F.M., Chaplin, J.C., Sanderson, D., Popov, A., Maffei, A., Ratchev, S., 2023. A framework for manufacturing system reconfiguration and optimisation utilising digital twins and modular artificial intelligence. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing* 82, 102524.
- Monostori, L., 2014. Cyber-physical production systems: Roots, expectations and r&d challenges. *Procedia cirp* 17, 9–13.
- Monostori, L., Kádár, B., Bauernhansl, T., Kondoh, S., Kumara, S., Reinhardt, G., Sauer, O., Schuh, G., Sihn, W., Ueda, K., 2016. Cyber-physical systems in manufacturing. *CIRP Annals* 65, 621–641.
- Mora-Cantalops, M., Sánchez-Alonso, S., García-Barriocanal, E., Sicilia, M.A., 2021. Traceability for trustworthy ai: A review of models and tools. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing* 5, 20.
- Nyakundi, N.B., 2026. Managing entanglement in ai-enabled safety-critical systems (aiscs), in: *Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC)*, IEEE. pp. 1511–1520.
- Orm, M.B., Jeunet, J., 2018. Time cost quality trade-off problems: a survey exploring the assessment of quality. *Computers & Industrial Engineering* 118, 319–328.
- Peres, R.S., Jia, X., Lee, J., Sun, K., Colombo, A.W., Barata, J., 2020. Industrial artificial intelligence in industry 4.0-systematic review, challenges and outlook. *IEEE Access* 8, 220121–220139.
- Pfeiffer, J., Ruder, S., Vulić, I., Ponti, E.M., 2023. Modular deep learning. *arXiv preprint doi:arXiv:2302.11529*.
- Pimenov, D.Y., Bustillo, A., Wojciechowski, S., Sharma, V.S., Gupta, M.K., Kuntoğlu, M., 2023. Artificial intelligence systems for tool condition monitoring in machining: Analysis and critical review. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* 34, 2079–2121.
- Plathottam, S.J., Rzonca, A., Lakhnori, R., Iloeje, C.O., 2023. A review of artificial intelligence applications in manufacturing operations. *Journal of Advanced Manufacturing and Processing* 5, e10159.
- Rabiser, R., Zoitl, A., 2021. Towards mastering variability in software-intensive cyber-physical production systems. *International Conference on Industry 4.0 and Smart Manufacturing (ISM)* 180, 50–59.
- Rahman, M., Khatoonabadi, S., Abdellatif, A., Samaana, H., Shihab, E., 2025. The impact of environment configurations on the stability of ai-enabled systems, in: *International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering (EASE)*, ACM. pp. 512–523.
- Rakholia, R., Suárez-Cetrulo, A.L., Singh, M., Carbajo, R.S., 2024. Advancing manufacturing through artificial intelligence: Current landscape, perspectives, best practices, challenges, and future direction. *IEEE Access* 12, 131621–131637.
- Rehman, H.U., Chaplin, J.C., Zarzycki, L., Ratchev, S., 2021. A framework for self-configuration in manufacturing production systems, in: *Doctoral Conference on Computing, Electrical and Industrial Systems*, Springer. pp. 71–79.
- Ross, N.S., Sheeba, P.T., Shibi, C.S., Gupta, M.K., Korkmaz, M.E., Sharma, V.S., 2024. A novel approach of tool condition monitoring in sustainable machining of ni alloy with transfer learning models. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* 35, 757–775.
- Rožanec, J.M., Križnar, K., Montini, E., Cutrona, V., Koehorst, E., Fortuna, B., Mladenčić, D., Emmanouilidis, C., 2023. Predicting operators' fatigue in a human in the artificial intelligence loop for defect detection in manufacturing. *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 56, 7609–7614.
- Saleh, K., Abdulsalam, H., 2025. Operationalizing iso/iec 42001: Requirements and conformance evidence for ai management systems, in: *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence for Sustainable Innovation (AI-SI)*, IEEE. pp. 1–4.
- Schlegel, M., Sattler, K.U., 2023. Management of machine learning lifecycle artifacts: A survey. *ACM SIGMOD Record* 51, 18–35.
- Schmidt, R.C., 1997. Managing delphi surveys using nonparametric statistical techniques. *Decision Sciences* 28, 763–774.
- Scholz, P., 2022. *Applikation maschinell lernender Systeme in der vernetzten adaptiven Produktion*. Ph.D. thesis. RWTH Aachen.
- Schuh, G., Scholz, P., 2019. Development of a framework for the systematic identification of ai application patterns in the manufacturing industry, in: *Portland International Conference on Management of Engineering and Technology (PICMET)*, IEEE. pp. 1–8.
- Schuh, G., Scholz, P., Leich, T., May, R., 2020. Identifying and analyzing data model requirements and technology potentials of machine learning systems in the manufacturing industry of the future, in: *International Scientific Conference on Information Technology and Management Science (ITMS)*, IEEE. pp. 1–10.
- Schuh, G., Scholz, P., Schorr, S., Harman, D., Möller, M., Heib, J., Bähre, D., et al., 2019. Prediction of workpiece quality: An application of machine learning in manufacturing industry, in: *6th International Conference on Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology (CSEIT-2019)*, AIRCC Publishing Corporation. pp. 189–202.
- Scotti, V., 2019. Artificial intelligence. *IEEE Instrumentation & Measurement Magazine* 23, 27–31.
- Semmelrock, H., Ross-Hellauer, T., Kopeinik, S., Theiler, D., Haberl, A., Thalmann, S., Kowald, D., 2025. Reproducibility in machine-learning-based research: Overview, barriers, and drivers. *AI Magazine* 46, e70002.
- Seródio, C., Mestre, P., Cabral, J., Gomes, M., Branco, F., 2024. Software and architecture orchestration for process control in industry 4.0 enabled by cyber-physical systems technologies. *Applied Sciences* 14, 2160.
- Sinha, S., Lee, Y.M., 2024. Challenges with developing and deploying ai models and applications in industrial systems. *Discover Artificial Intelligence* 4, 55.
- Soldatos, J., 2024. *Artificial intelligence in manufacturing: Enabling intelligent, flexible and cost-effective production through AI*. Springer.
- Soori, M., Arezoo, B., Dastres, R., 2023. Machine learning and artificial intelligence in cnc machine tools, a review. *Sustainable Manufacturing and Service Economics* 2, 100009.
- Steimers, A., Schneider, M., 2022. Sources of risk of ai systems. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19, 3641.
- Tarafdar, R., 2025. Human-ai collaboration in workflow optimization: A framework for hybrid decision systems in automation-heavy industries. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology* 11, 3594–3613.
- Todescato, M., Braholli, O., Chaltsev, D., Di Blasio, I., Don, D., Egger, G., Emig, J., Pasetti Monizza, G., Sacco, P., Siegele, D., et al., 2023. Sustainable manufacturing through application of reconfigurable and intelligent systems in production processes: a system perspective. *Scientific Reports* 13, 22374.
- Uren, V., Edwards, J.S., 2023. Technology readiness and the organizational journey towards ai adoption: An empirical study. *International Journal of Information Management* 68, 102588.
- Van Dyck, M., Lüttgens, D., Piller, F.T., Brenk, S., 2023. Interconnected digital twins and the future of digital manufacturing: Insights from a delphi study. *Journal of Product Innovation Management* 40, 475–505.
- Varela-Vaca, A.J., et al., 2021. CARMEN: A framework for the verification and diagnosis of the specification of security requirements in cyber-physical systems. *Computers in Industry* 132, 103524.
- Vernon, W., 2009. The delphi technique: A review. *International Journal of Therapy and Rehabilitation* 16, 69–76.
- Von Der Gracht, H.A., 2012. Consensus measurement in delphi studies: Review and implications for future quality assurance. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 79, 1525–1536.
- Wan, J., Tang, S., Shu, Z., Li, D., Wang, S., Imran, M., Vasilakos, A.V., 2016. Software-defined industrial internet of things in the context of

- industry 4.0. *IEEE Sensors Journal* 16, 7373–7380.
- Wang, J., Ma, Y., Zhang, L., Gao, R.X., Wu, D., 2018. Deep learning for smart manufacturing: Methods and applications. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems* 48, 144–156.
- Weber, M., Engert, M., Schaffer, N., Weking, J., Krcmar, H., 2023. Organizational capabilities for ai implementation—coping with inscrutability and data dependency in ai. *Information Systems Frontiers* 25, 1549–1569.
- Xiang, W., Yu, K., Han, F., Fang, L., He, D., Han, Q.L., 2023. Advanced manufacturing in industry 5.0: A survey of key enabling technologies and future trends. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* 20, 1055–1068.
- Xu, T., Zhou, Y., 2015. Systems approaches to tackling configuration errors: A survey. *ACM Computing Surveys* 47, 1–41.
- Zdravković, M., Panetto, H., Weichhart, G., 2021. Ai-enabled enterprise information systems for manufacturing. *Enterprise Information Systems* 16, 668–720.
- Zhang, G., Ye, H., Lin, Y., 2011. Modelling quality attributes in feature models in software product line engineering, in: *International Conference on Software Technologies (ICSOFTE)*, SciTePress. pp. 249–254.
- Zhang, W., Yang, D., Wang, H., 2019. Data-driven methods for predictive maintenance of industrial equipment: A survey. *IEEE Systems Journal* 13, 2213–2227.
- Zimmermann, T., 2016. Card-sorting: From text to themes, in: *Perspectives on Data Science for Software Engineering*. Elsevier, pp. 137–141.